

Background

Arthropod diversity at all trophic levels has been found to correlate with plant diversity¹. The Fynbos biome is remarkably rich in floral diversity compared to the adjacent relictual forest biome, despite the relatively recent origins of the Fynbos (although some lineages may be very old). These two vegetation types are separated by biotic and abiotic characteristics², both of which are likely to affect invertebrate diversity³. Collembola are an understudied, but ecologically important group of arthropods. The genus *Seira* is especially diverse in the Cape Floristic Region (CFR)⁴, and here we will investigate the diversity patterns and phylogenetic relationships of *Seira* in the Fynbos and Southern Afrotemperate Forest (SAF) across the CFR.

- Hypotheses**
- *Seira* species richness is expected to be higher in the Fynbos than the SAF.
 - The species turnover of *Seira* should be relatively high among these two distinct vegetation types, resulting in high regional diversity.
 - Abiotic factors may influence the *Seira* species diversity.
 - The SAF *Seira* taxa are expected to be older than Fynbos taxa, and each may form a monophyletic group.

Fig.2. The spatial scales at which the three diversity components will be measured.

Preliminary results and discussion

A phylogeny of *Seira* based on COI gene suggests that most species are habitat specialists and are restricted to a specific vegetation type. Thus species turnover may be high between the two vegetation types. However, Fynbos and SAF taxa do not form distinct monophyletic groups indicating that habitat switches may have occurred in the past.

Fig. 1. The eleven sampling localities within pristine Fynbos (■) and Southern Afrotemperate Forest (■) vegetation types.

Materials and Methods

The research will be conducted across the CFR of South Africa (see Fig.1). Litter samples will be collected and environmental factors will be recorded, such as temperature, relative humidity and soil properties. *Seira* will be extracted using Tullgren funnels⁵. Specimens will be identified to morphospecies level using taxonomic keys and DNA barcoding. The alpha (α), beta (β) and gamma (γ) diversity of *Seira* assemblages will be calculated (Fig.2). Multivariate analyses (PRIMER V5.0) will be used to compare the *Seira* species diversity between vegetation types, and Fynbos plant genera. The relationships between abiotic factors and species richness and abundance will be analysed using Generalised Linear Models. The barcoding data of the COI gene will be used to ascertain phylogenetic relationships of *Seira* species (MrBayes v.3.2.1).

Acknowledgments: Funding for this project is provided by DST-NRF Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology. C. Janion and L. Deharveng for taxonomic advice. Barcoding funded by BOLD. SANParks and CapeNature for collection permits. Photographs: C. Janion & J. Allen. Map: F. Tererai.

Fig.3. The phylogenetic relationships of *Seira* species in the Fynbos (■) and Southern Afrotemperate Forest (■) of the CFR derived from a Bayesian Inference analysis using 658-bp of the COI. Nodal support of ≥0.95 posterior probabilities (PP) is shown. Representative images are given for various clades.

References: 1) Proches, S., Forest, F., Veldtman, R., Chown, S.L., Cowling, R.M., Johnson, S.D., Richardson, D.M. & Savolainen, V. 2009. Mol Phylogenet Evol. 51, 94-99. 2) Campbell B.M. & Moll, E.J. 1977. Vegetatio, 34(2), 105-1145. 3) Pryke, J.S. & Samways, M.J. 2008. Biodiversity Conserv. 17, 3027-3043. 4) Janion, C., Bedos, A., Bengtsson, J., Deharveng, L., Jansen van Vuuren, B., Leinaas, H.P., Liu, A., Malmström, A., Porco, D. & Chown, S.L. 2011. S. Afr. J. Sci. 107, 5) Macfadyen, A. 1953. J. Anim. Ecol. 22, 65-77.